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Characterizing Human Walking Dynamics Across Age: A Control Engineering Approach

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Abstract:

Introduction While various models and studies have investigated the simulation and theoretical description of human gait, previous research has not considered irregular situations such as slipping and tripping. However, understanding these situations could be crucial and provide insight into assessing dynamic balance, a factor that is closely linked to the risk of falling. The first step is to investigate the system under normal walking using a participant group that includes people who are particularly susceptible to an increased risk of falling, such as older adults or people with certain health conditions that have so far been neglected in the literature.

Methods In this study a control engineering approach was used to estimate the parameters of the human gait system. A total of 42 subjects aged 18 to 78 years, with different body masses and walking speeds, were analyzed. Measurements were conducted on a treadmill with integrated force plates, while participants wore inertial measurement units (IMUs) at lumbar level and were filmed with cameras.

Results The calculated spring-mass-damping model parameters, including stiffness (k) and damping (c), varied widely among participants, with stiffness ranging from 4.45 to 45.53 kN/m and damping from 0.26 to 2.13 kNs/m. Contrary to previous findings, no linear relationships were observed between stiffness or damping and velocity, age, or mass. Outliers were identified and related in a plausible way to visual inspection.

Conclusion In conclusion, our study successfully characterized human walking during periodic excitation for a diverse participant group using a simple control engineering approach, yielding comparable results to previous studies. Our results pave the way for future investigations to analyze the response of an individual participant to irregular gait perturbations.

Keywords: spring-mass-damping model, control engineering approach, second-order system, dynamic balance, perturbation excitation

1 Introduction

Walking is a fundamental aspect of human functionality and is closely linked to an individual's health status. Consequently, the monitoring and analysis of gait serve as valuable tools to reveal individual gait abnormalities. Over time, numerous models have emerged to simulate and theoretically describe human walking. These models include the inverted pendulum [1–3], bipedal robot models [4, 5], neuromuscular models [6, 7], and spring-mass-damping (SMD) models [8, 9], which are often used for studies on human-structure interaction [10]. Within each model, different methods are used in the literature for system identification. However, previous studies have primarily concentrated on parameter extraction in healthy young to middle-aged individuals, without emphasizing comparisons between different individuals. Additionally, parameters are typically extracted for standard activities such as standing, normal walking, and jumping [11, 12], with irregular situations being not investigated.

Our research is motivated by the long-term goal of understanding individuals' reactions to unexpected gait perturbations, such as slipping or tripping. This could potentially lead to a way of assessing dynamic balance, which is closely linked to the risk of falling, which can be a major health risk, especially for older people. To achieve this goal, the focus lies in a first step on characterizing the individual walking systems in vertical direction within a diverse participant group under continuous excitation (normal walking). In contrast to previous studies, the group of participants includes people from a wide range of age groups and different health conditions. Using a simple control engineering approach of modelling human walking as a second-order system (PT2) (similar to [13]), the parameters of the transfer function were estimated and matched with those of a spring-mass-damping system. The relations between the characteristics of the participants and the calculated values are analyzed, and conspicuous outliers are identified and investigated in more detail.

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Fig. 1: The upper row shows the participants' characteristics age, velocity v and mass m . The lower row shows the calculated parameters stiffness k , damping c , eigenfrequency f_0 and mass M for the spring-mass-damping model.

2 Methods

A total of 42 participants, ranging in age from 18 to 78 years, were included. The participants body masses varied in a range of $m = [53.7, 114]$ kg, and self-selected walking velocities ranging from $v = [0.72, 1.67]$ m/s (see upper row of Figure 1). The study was approved by the medical ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg (number 2021-093). All participants provided written informed consent to voluntarily participate in the study and received financial compensation on an hourly basis. All measurements were conducted on a treadmill (MGait Motek Medical B.V., Amsterdam, the Netherlands), with built in force-plates, to ensure standardized walking conditions. Participants wore an inertial measurement unit (IMU) (Opal V1, Mobility Lab™ (ML), APDM, Inc., Portland, OR, USA) positioned at the lumbar region to capture motion data during walking and were filmed with cameras (Azure Kinect DK, Microsoft, Redmond, WA, USA). Each participant performed a one-minute walk on the treadmill after determining their preferred walking velocity. The start and stop process at the beginning and end of the walking trial was removed and the data were smoothed and low-pass filtered at 2.5 Hz.

The dynamics of human walking were modeled using a second-order transfer function

$$H(s) = \frac{A}{s^2 + Bs + C}, \quad (1)$$

with the ground reaction force $F(t)$ as an input signal and the acceleration $a(t)$ at the lumbar as an output signal. The parameters A , B and C can be physically interpreted by using the spring-mass-damping (SMD) model. This model represents the human body as a spring-mass-damper system, where the force $F(t)$ leads to a displacement $x(t)$ of the lumbar region

[14]. The differential equation for such a system reads

$$\ddot{x}(t) + \frac{c}{M}\dot{x}(t) + \frac{k}{M}x(t) = \frac{F(t)}{M}, \quad (2)$$

with damping c , mass M and vertical stiffness k . From this the transfer function can be calculated by the deviation of the laplace transformed input $F(s)$ and output $X(s)$. Under the assumption that the displacement of the lumbar follows an oscillation so that $x(t) \propto \sin(\omega_0 t)$ with angular frequency $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_0 = \sqrt{\frac{k}{M}}$, the laplace transformed acceleration yields $A(s) = -\omega_0^2 X(s)$. With this the transfer function between the force $F(t)$ and the acceleration $a(t)$ yields the equation

$$H(s) = \frac{A(s)}{F(s)} = -\frac{\omega_0^2}{M(s^2 + \frac{c}{M}s + \frac{k}{M})}. \quad (3)$$

This results in the following relations

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= \frac{1}{2\pi}\sqrt{C}, & M &= -\frac{C}{A}, \\ k &= -\frac{C^2}{A}, & c &= -\frac{BC}{A}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The transfer function for each participant was calculated using MATLAB's tfest function. The accuracy of the fit for each transfer function was assessed using MATLAB's compare function. Only participants with an accuracy of 70% or higher were included.

3 Results

The lower row of Figure 1 shows the calculated values for the spring-mass-damping model parameters: stiffness k , damping c , eigenfrequency f_0 and mass M for the different participants. The calculated values for spring stiffness (k) ranged from 4.45 to 45.53 kN/m, whereby all values out of [4.45, 31.90] kN/m were considered as outliers. The damping coefficient (c) ranged from 0.26 to 2.13 kNs/m, whereby all values out of [0.26, 1.54] kNs/m were considered as outliers. Figure 2 shows the calculated parameters in relation to the characteristics of the participants. A significant linear relation was found between the damping and the mass m with a value of 0.18 for R^2 . No linear relation was found between the spring stiffness and the velocity or the mass m as well as for the damping c and the velocity v , contrary to previous studies [10, 13]. Also no linear relation was found between the stiffness or damping and the participants' age. Linear regression analysis between the calculated masses (M) and the actual masses (m) of the participants revealed a systematic shift of 3.51 kg between the two variables.

In order to validate the stiffness and damping, a few noticeable subjects are examined in more detail below. The data

Fig. 2: Calculated parameters stiffness k , damping c , eigenfrequency f_0 and mass M for the spring-mass-damping model in relation to the characteristics of the participants mass m , velocity v and age. The solid red line represents the linear regression, while the dashed red lines indicate the 95% confidence bounds.

for these participants are displayed in Table 1. The lowest stiffness was observed for a young (22 year old) participant (P1) with $k = 4.45$ kN/m. The person also exhibited a low damping with $c = 0.26$ kNs/m and was walking relatively slow with $v = 0.89$ m/s. In contrast to that a 37 year old participant (P2) exhibited values in the normal range with $k = 11.35$ kN/m and $c = 0.75$ kNs/m at a walking speed of $v = 1.25$ m/s. The highest vertical stiffness $k = 45.53$ kN/m was observed for a 59 year old woman (P3), who was walking quite fast with $v = 1.67$ m/s. She yields a damping in the normal range of $c = 1.35$ kNs/m. Another participant yields with $k = 23.81$ kN/m not only a high vertical stiffness, but also with $c = 1.48$ kNs/m a high damping. This was a 76 year old woman (P4) that walked very slow with $v = 0.72$ m/s. A 77 year old man (P5) also shows a higher vertical stiffness as normal $k = 31.90$ kN/m and a very high damping $c = 2.02$ kNs/m. However another 77 year old man (P6) yields values for the stiffness $k = 11.33$ kN/m and the damping $c = 0.51$ kNs/m, that are in the normal range.

4 Discussion & Conclusion

The aim of the study was to characterize human walking during a periodic excitation for a diverse participant group with a simple control engineering approach. The results show comparable values for the physical parameters as previous studies [9, 13, 15]. However, there are also some subjects who exhibit values outside the normal range. To check their plausibility, the recorded videos were examined for these subjects.

The participant P1 showed a low stiffness and a low damping. This stands in good agreement with the visual impression through the video. Here the impact of the foot contact could be visually observed to travel through the body and causing vibrations of the upper thigh of the person. This is an indicator that the excitation travels nearly undamped through the legs of the person. For participant P2 no abnormalities in walking were observed, as the values suggested. The video of participant P3 revealed that the person walked not just rather fast but also very energetically and walking to the front without moving up and down a lot. This relates to the really high vertical stiffness, that was found. Participant P4 walked very insecure, was very scared while walking and moved the whole body while walking. The strained walking of the person may explain not only the high vertical stiffness but also the high damping that was found. Participant P5 seemed to have a more rigid walk than normal, which is in good agreement with the very high stiffness and damping that was found. As an example it can be seen at P6 that the high stiffness and damping is not a matter of age and more a matter of the way of walking. The found systematic difference between the actual mass m and the calculated mass M of 3.51 kg can be partly explained by the equipment the participants wore. Since the study was part of a larger study the participants wore a lot of equipment (three smartphones, nine IMUs, two hearing aids, three bags, secure harness), which explains the difference in masses. The fact that, contrary to existing literature, we found no linear correlations between stiffness k and the damping c with walking speed could be due to the fact that previous studies included only a few subjects, all of whom were young to middle-aged and able-bodied. To further explore these results, future stud-

Tab. 1: participants' characteristics (age, gait-affecting diagnoses, velocity v , and mass m) together with the calculated parameter for the spring-mass-damping model f_0, M, k and c for a few selected participants

ID	age [year]	gait-affecting diagnoses	v [m/s]	m [kg]	f_0 [Hz]	M [kg]	k [kN/m]	c [kNs/m]	fit [%]
P1	22	nothing	0.89	53.7	1.38	59.0	4.45	0.26	71
P2	37	small leg length difference	1.25	75.8	1.91	78.81	11.35	0.75	82
P3	59	scoliosis, arthritis	1.67	61.6	4.21	65.09	45.53	1.35	89
P4	76	knee implants	0.72	100.9	2.42	102.82	23.81	1.48	73
P5	77	myocardial infarction, stroke	0.89	89.1	2.97	91.38	31.90	2.02	79
P6	77	nothing	1.22	79	1.88	81.54	11.33	0.51	83

ies should increase participant numbers to ensure diversity in a well-controlled setting, enabling more targeted investigations of factors like age and physical ability on model parameters.

It was shown that it is possible to calculate meaningful physical parameters for a diverse participant group using a control engineering approach that models human walking in vertical direction. The values agree well with the literature and outliers can be plausibly linked to the visual impression. Future analyses should include the investigation of irregular perturbation excitation as this could offer a promising way to assess a person's reactive dynamic balance. Next steps should also involve extending the model to the horizontal plane.

Author Statement

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References

- [1] Kajita, Shuuji, and Kazuo Tani. "Study of dynamic biped locomotion on rugged terrain-derivation and application of the linear inverted pendulum mode." Proceedings. 1991 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. IEEE Computer Society, 1991.
- [2] Buczek, F. L., Cooney, K. M., Walker, M. R., Rainbow, M. J., Concha, M. C., & Sanders, J. O. (2006). Performance of an inverted pendulum model directly applied to normal human gait. *Clinical Biomechanics*, 21(3), 288-296.
- [3] Kuo, Arthur D. "The six determinants of gait and the inverted pendulum analogy: A dynamic walking perspective." *Human movement science*, 26(4), 617-656, 2007.
- [4] Chevallereau, C., Bessonnet, G., Abba, G., & Aoustin, Y. (Eds.). (2013). *Bipedal robots: modeling, design and walking synthesis*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [5] Grizzle, J. W., Chevallereau, C., Sinnet, R. W., & Ames, A. D. (2014). Models, feedback control, and open problems of 3D bipedal robotic walking. *Automatica*, 50(8), 1955-1988.
- [6] Song, Seungmoon, and Hartmut Geyer. "Regulating speed and generating large speed transitions in a neuromuscular human walking model." Proceedings of the 2012 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. IEEE, 2012.
- [7] Prochazka, A., Gosgnach, S., Capaday, C., & Geyer, H. (2017). Neuromuscular models for locomotion. In *Bioinspired Legged Locomotion* (pp. 401-453). Butterworth-Heinemann.
- [8] Shahabpoor, Erfan, Aleksandar Pavic, and Vitomir Racic. "Identification of mass-spring-damper model of walking humans." *Structures*, 5, Elsevier, 2016.
- [9] Nikooyan, Ali Asadi, and Amir Abbas Zadpoor. "Mass-spring-damper modelling of the human body to study running and hopping—an overview." Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine, 225(12), 1121-1135, 2011.
- [10] Pfeil, M.S., Varela, W.D., de Paula Amador da Costa, N. Experimental calibration of a one degree of freedom biodynamic model to simulate human walking-structure interaction. *Engineering Structures*, 262, 2022.
- [11] Serpell, B. G., Ball, N. B., Scarvell, J. M., & Smith, P. N. (2012). A review of models of vertical, leg, and knee stiffness in adults for running, jumping or hopping tasks. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 30(13), 1347-1363.
- [12] Bret, C., Rahmani, A., Dufour, A. B., Messonnier, L., & Lacour, J. R. (2002). Leg Strength and Stiffness As Ability Factors in 100 M Sprint Running. *The Journal of Sports Medicine and Physical Fitness*, 42(3), 274-281.
- [13] Bertos, G. A., Childress, D. S., & Gard, S. A. (2019). A 2nd-Order Model of the Vertical Impedance of the Locomotor System During Human Walking. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, 1(3), 169-176.
- [14] Wang, H., Chen, J., & Brownjohn, J. M. W. (2017). Parameter identification of pedestrian's spring-mass-damper model by ground reaction force records through a particle filter approach. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 411, 409-421.
- [15] Silva, F. T., & Pimentel, R. L. (2011). Biodynamic walking model for vibration serviceability of footbridges in vertical direction. Proceeding of the 8th International Conference on Structural Dynamics (Eurodyn'11).